

1 **Sox11 has functions in pluripotency.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of Sox11 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic
11 stem cells.

12 Citations

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17 expression in mouse embryonic stem cells. Nature cell biology, 9(6), pp.625-635.